

VOCABULARY COMPOSITION IN PRIMARY-GRADE MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES: METHOD OF TEACHING WORD-FORMING AND WORD-CONNECTING ADVERBS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada morfemika nimaligi, morfemikaning turlari asos morfema, affiksial morfema haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Morfemikani o'quvchilarga o'rgatish metodikasi bilan ham tanishishingiz mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Asos morfema, affiks morfema, so'z yasovchi morfema, shakl yasovchi morfema.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о том, что такое морфемика, виды морфемы, базовая морфема, аффиксальная морфема. Также вы можете ознакомиться с методикой преподавания морфемы студентам.

Ключевые слова: базовая морфема, аффиксная морфема, словообразовательная морфема, формообразующая морфема.

Annotation: This article provides information on what morphemics are, types of morphemics, base morpheme, affixal morpheme. You can also get acquainted with the methodology of teaching morphemics to students.

Key words: Base morpheme, affix morpheme, word-forming morpheme, form-forming morpheme.

Forms, methods and methods of organizing the joint activity of the teacher and the student in teaching the mother tongue are developing and updating in connection with the improvement of the educational system. As methods of teaching, explanatory method, interview method, analysis-synthesis method, independent work method, inductive-deductive methods were used in the organization of native language classes. Nowadays, it is required to pass the classes using various modern methods. It is important that these methods are suitable for the child's age and the topic being studied, and especially, they are intended to make the topics of the mother tongue easier to explain to the students.

In order to determine the lexical meaning of a word, dividing it into morphemes has its theoretical basis in the science of language. The department of morphemics is the department that studies the smallest meaningful parts of the language. The subject of study of the department of morphemics is the morpheme.

In order to understand the meaning of a word in primary class mother tongue classes, it is done by dividing it into morphemes. A word consists of a base (stem) and a suffix. A morpheme is the smallest, indivisible part of a word. The morpheme is divided into two types: The root morpheme (base) is a morpheme that necessarily takes part in the word and has a lexical meaning. Affixal morpheme (suffix) - a morpheme that does not independently mean lexical meaning, but forms lexical and grammatical meanings of the word. For example, in the words gulami, gulla, gul is a root morpheme, -lar, -ni, -la are affixal morphemes.

In working on the morphemic structure of words, the teacher's tasks include:

-s , students will learn one of the main ways to determine the lexical meaning of a word.

In this case, the task of the teacher is to create the most favorable conditions for students to learn that the lexical meaning and morphemic structure of words are related to each other, and on this basis, to guide them to clarify their vocabulary;

-elementary knowledge of word formation is also important for students to understand the main source of enrichment of our language with new words. A new word is formed from morphemes existing in the language, based on certain methods and models. Observing the formation of words has a positive effect on the formation of an active attitude to words in students, leads to an understanding of the laws of language development;

- getting to know the basics of word formation allows enriching students' vocabulary with knowledge about the environment. Concepts about objects, processes, events are expressed in words. Determining the relationship between words in terms of meaning and structure is based on the relationship between mutually related concepts . For example, the words *work, worker, flower, florist* are related. The concepts are therefore connected according to the structure of meaning . If students really know the relationship of words according to their meaning and structure, they will deeply imagine and know the connection between the objects, processes, and events that exist in the environment ;

- understanding the importance of the morpheme in the word, as well as knowing the semantic meaning of the adverbs, students have clear speech affects the formation. The task of the teacher is to teach students not only to understand the lexical meaning of the word, but also to consciously use words with specific adverbs in the context;

- studying the morphemic structure of the word is also of great importance in the formation of spelling skills. Formation of the skill of correct spelling of roots and suffixes on a theoretical basis requires appropriate application of phonetic , word formation, and grammatical knowledge. Therefore, one of the important tasks of studying the morphemic structure of a word is to create the basis of knowledge and skills necessary for the formation of the skill of writing the stem and suffixes correctly;

- the study of the morphemic structure of the word is important in developing the mental abilities of students, in particular, in the formation of special mental skills necessary for the conscious learning of the word as a language unit. The task of the teacher is to create an environment in which students develop mental activity, analyze, and compare skills with the assimilation of knowledge in the educational process.

Studying the morphemic structure of the word in accordance with the program of the native language of primary classes begins in the 3rd grade. In the 4th grade, it is planned to improve the knowledge about the structure of the word. The study of the topic is divided into four stages:

The first stage is the preparatory stage for learning word formation. The task of this stage is to prepare students to understand the meaning and structure of words with the same root.

The second stage is to introduce the properties of words with the same root and the meaning of all morphemes.

The third stage is the method of studying the characteristics and significance of the root, word-forming and form-forming affixes.

The fourth stage is to work on the composition of the word in connection with the study of word groups. In the system of studying the morphemic structure of the word, the purpose of this stage is to deepen the knowledge about the importance of the word-forming suffix in word formation and the importance of the form-forming suffix in changing the word form; is to prepare students to understand the formation features of nouns, adjectives, and verbs.

Asos means an independent lexical meaning, a leading part that can be an answer to a question, a part of a sentence. The base of the word my country is vatan +im. Suffix is a category that is added to the base and does not express an independent lexical meaning, cannot be an answer to a question and cannot be a part of a sentence, but gives a new meaning to the base, it is a means of loading additional meaning, as well as linking words to words. Adverbs, in turn, are divided into two types: 1. Word-forming adverbs - adverbs added to the base and giving new meaning: work+chi, flower+don, book+khan, gate+bon ,tila+k. 2. Form-builders are adverbs added to the base and adding additional meaning to the word (lexical form-builders) and linking words to words (syntactic form-builders).

Work on word-forming additions. The main task of learning this morpheme is to familiarize students with the importance of the word-forming suffix in a word and, on this basis, to develop the ability to consciously use a word-forming suffix in their speech. It is important for students to understand that a word-forming suffix can be used to create a word with a new lexical meaning.

Learning features of the form builder plugin. The linguistic essence of each morpheme is unique, and the methodology of its study also has its own characteristics. Grammatical task is leading in form-forming adverb, thus it differs from word-forming adverb. A formative adverb is a means of expressing the grammatical meaning of an adverb. Students do not understand the function of form-forming adverb without knowing the grammatical meaning of the word. In addition, the form-forming suffix expresses several meanings .

As students learn the morphemic structure of words and word formation, they begin to make conscious use of dividing words into morphemes. They learn the lexical meaning of artificial words based on the semantic similarity of the words. Managing the importance of working on the morphemic structure of words with interactive methods during the lesson organized by the teacher has a strong effect. Some methods for teaching word tracking:

"Find your neighbor" method. The class is divided into two groups. The teacher says a word, the first group tells the meaning of the word, the second group divides the content of the word. The teacher evaluates this process. The game lasts for 1 minute. continues. Then it is understood that the lexical meaning of the word is close to the morphemic meaning. For example:

Group 1: Unsalted - no salt. Official - a person with a position.

Group 2: Without salt. Salt+without, Mansabdar. Mansab+dar.

"Find me" method . This can be done with a group or the whole class. The teacher gives specially made words. One student chooses one of the given words. He turns to his peers with a question. For example: Question: I like flowers, I plant flowers, I take care of them. Answer: Flower + what. Question: I have a lot of money. What kind of person am I. Answer: Money + money.

"Koptok" method . This method helps the student to improve his oral speech and speed. The teacher throws the ball at the student by asking a question or adding a word, and the student creates a new word and reads it. The teacher will have to throw the ball back.

"Who's the smartest" method. Increases students' thinking, ingenuity and agility. This method can be played in a group or individually. The person who finds the most words is encouraged.

"Kim chaqqon?"

A collection of words and suffixes scattered on a white background, intended for a word game. The words and suffixes include:

- shirin, gul, -la, -xon, gul
- li, zarar, -siz, -dosh, -dor, -chi
- quvvat, tayyor, navbat, teng
- chi, tuz, ish, -lik, vatan, muruvvat, xona
- gul, kasal, vatan, -dor, -dosh
- foйда, -chi, qiziq, -dor, kitob
- li, -dor, kuy, maslahat, gul
- aql, rang, jimjima, hosil, -dosh
- pul, -dosh, tik, gul

"Pictures speak" method. In this method, students are shown pictures. Looking at the picture, they have to find imaginary words. For example, we can find imaginary words from the pictures below. Fish+chi, cook+paz, heal+blind .

"Where is my house" method. In this method, students are given words. Students have to place the words in their nests.

"Mening uyim qayerda"

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